

MANAGEMENT PROGRAMMING IMPROVING PARENTS' PARTICIPATION IN LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN KINDERGARTEN

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Abstract

One of the important issues of education that is often studied from various perspectives is character building, the lack of parents in understanding parenting material, it is deemed necessary for parental participation, as well as in early childhood education. The parenting program is expected to increase parental participation in learning activities in Kindergarten. The purpose of this study was to obtain an overview and analyze the parenting program, this study used a qualitative descriptive. The research data were collected by using observation, interview, and documentation techniques. The research location is Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency. The results of research on parenting program management in increasing parental participation in learning activities in Kindergarten (1) in planning parenting programs have not involved stakeholders so that the program is not sharp and touches all program domains, (2) in the implementation of parenting programs does not involve stakeholders to play a role active so that the community is less active in supporting institutional programs, (3) in evaluating the parenting program, parents have not assessed so that the problems faced by students cannot be identified early on. The conclusion from this research is that the institution has not involved stakeholders and parents optimally as a support for the progress of the institution

Keywords: parenting program management, participation, and learning.

A. PRELIMINARY

Entering the development of education, the quality of human resources received attention in relation to efforts to improve the quality of life of the nation. In this case the government has explicitly emphasized in realizing quality human resources that can be pursued through education. The government's attention in the field of education is emphasized on education for early childhood.

Parenting is an educational effort carried out by the family by utilizing the resources available in the family and the environment in the form of independent learning activities. Parenting is a continuous process of interaction between parents and their children which includes the following activities: nourishing, guiding, and protecting children as they grow and develop.

The purpose of this study was to obtain an overview and analyze about, planning, organizing, implementing, parenting in kindergarten. An important issue in developing children's self, has recently become one of the important issues in the field of education. The problem that is often studied from various points of view is the formation of character in children. This can be seen in the way children behave which is an accumulation of various aspects of the formation of a good self. When viewed from the point of view of Developmental Psychology, of course the character that is formed is not something that suddenly exists, but is the result of the process of a child's life journey which is formed from biological maturity and psychological development.

Maturity refers to the changes that occur naturally and spontaneously. Meanwhile, changes related to psychological development are related to learning experiences obtained from the surrounding environment, therefore one thing that needs to be considered is how the process of education and care is obtained by children, thus forming a meaningful learning experience for themselves. According to Yuliani N. Sujiono, (2011: 6) Early childhood is a golden period of development at that time there was an extraordinary surge, Early Childhood Education is a form of education that focuses on laying the foundation for physical growth and development (fine motor coordination). And rude), intelligence (thinking power, creativity, emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence), socio-emotional (behavioral and religious attitudes) language and communication, in accordance with the uniqueness and stages of development that are passed by early childhood.

Ratna Megawangi explains in her book *Character Parenting Space, Being a Smart Parent to Awakening Children's Character* (1: 2007). That parenting refers to the atmosphere of teaching and learning activities that emphasize warmth, not towards a one-way or emotionless education. Thus, parenting is how to educate parents to children either directly or indirectly. Parenting concerns all the daily behavior of parents, whether directly related to children or not, which can be caught or seen by their children, with the hope that what is given to children (caregiving) will have positive implications for their lives, especially for religion, self, nation. As well as the country, resulting in three research questions to analyze

- 1) Planning a Parenting Program in Kindergarten
- 2) Implementation of Parenting Programs in Kindergarten
- 3) Evaluations carried out in the Parenting Program in Kindergarten.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

Through this descriptive research, it is hoped that the author will get a clear picture of parenting in Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency. The description of the research results obtained is in the form of a description or explanation in the form of a narrative about various kinds of opinions of the informants objectively regarding the parenting program to Increase Parental Participation in School Activities in Kindergarten.

The data collection mechanism is obtained from data sources or respondents, this is done in order to complement each other, so that the data can be carried out smoothly and in accordance with the objectives, this research uses the following data collection techniques:

a. Interview

Interviews are one way of obtaining research data in qualitative research to obtain clearer data and information regarding issues related to research, so the authors conducted interviews with school principals at Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency related to the parenting program.

b. Observation

Observation is one way of collecting data. Observations were made to observe directly about all programs carried out by research subjects who became the focus of research. This observation technique, researchers use when observing the activities carried out by research subjects in conducting parenting programs at Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency.

c. Documentation Study

The documentation study was conducted on the principal's work program related to the parenting program at Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structured planning and targeted evaluations will help institutions increase the potential of students and overcome existing obstacles and obstacles, as well as increase the success of institutions in implementing parenting guidance programs to increase parental participation in learning activities in kindergarten. In this section, the research findings will be described and analyzed using relevant theoretical studies, so that a model for planning, implementing, and evaluating the right parenting program for kindergarten can be obtained.

1. Parenting Program Planning

Parenting program planning is a plan that is carried out together with class teachers, school principals and institutions to make a parenting program service plan about phenomena that often occur in the development of contemporary students against negative events, (Sutirna, 2015: 164-165). The institution understands the parenting program as an effort to help parents know how to care for students to have potential, be independent, confident, qualified, superior, and competitive through training, habituation, direction, and coaching. This understanding starts from the goal established institution. The kindergartens studied, have shown their commitment to developing and integrating parenting programs into the non-academic teaching and coaching process for parents. However, in seeking guidance and counseling programs, madrasas must really plan parenting programs more carefully.

Proper planning requires planning principles as indicators of achievement, Terry put forward planning principles as follows, To be able to formulate an effective plan, it is necessary for people to reach all the important facts available, then face these facts and incorporate them into plans, actions required by these facts (Terry, 2012: 202).

At the planning stage, the managerial role of the principal must be very clear, the principal plans learning programs to provide meaningful learning experiences for students through parenting programs, therefore parenting programs must be prepared and planned to be more focused and effective in helping students achieve competence in accordance with the requirements in the parenting objectives. The achievement of parenting goals can be seen from how many indicators that have been set can be achieved. Meaningful parenting activities will have a broad impact on parents' understanding, including not only memorizing and

understanding parenting material that is learned theoretically but also implementing and implementing it in real terms.

School development plans need to be clearly formulated both in the long, medium and short term. The long term can be formulated in a strategic plan, which includes: vision, mission, goals, policies, strategies, and programs for a period of 5-10 years. The medium term includes strategies and programs that will be realized within 3-5 years. The short term includes programs that are prepared and realized every academic year. Good planning requires the involvement of all school stakeholders, such as principals, teachers, staff, students, supervisors, parents/school committees, and the education board. Meanwhile, organizing Parenting Parent's Day is a committee directly from the respective homeroom teacher, so that all kinds of activities regarding this program are handled directly by the homeroom teacher. However, the person responsible for the existence of this program remains entirely with the principal as the school leader.

2. Parenting Program Management

Implementation is part of the management process. This section deals with setting the structure through determining activities to achieve the goals of a business as a whole, as well as its parts. It also includes grouping activities, assignments, delegation of authority to carry out work, establishing coordination, authority for information relations, both vertically and horizontally in the organizational structure.

The implementation of this parenting activity is to introduce parenting techniques and provide insight to parents in the correct way of parenting. This activity uses methods in the form of giving material, demonstration, question and answer session and face to face with the material. The benefits of this parenting activity are considered very important for all parties because it can support school education, parenting programs run as expected, and the position of the institution becomes more qualified and recognized among the community.

Basically the implementation process will never be separated from the planning stage, where the implementation process is an application in the form of real activities from what has been determined in the planning stage. Likewise in the process of implementing the parenting program at Muhaimah Kindergarten, West Bandung Regency, through the planning process first. If in planning, managers and educators plan and determine things such as time, material, and place to the media or tools needed, then the implementation process will not be far from these things.

This is in accordance with what Westa (1985, p.17) in Arifin (2010) states that implementation is an activity or effort carried out to carry out all plans and policies that have been formulated and determined, equipped with all the needs, tools and equipment. - The tools needed, who implements it, where the implementation starts and how it should be implemented.

In its implementation, it emphasizes discussion and sharing with various problems faced by parents in the process of educating their children at home. The material presented in parenting activities is matters relating to the growth and development of children, parenting patterns at

home and more emphasis on parental problems in dealing with children so that they can foster child-friendly family behavior.

The speakers in the parenting program activities at Muhaimah Kindergarten are the managers and educators. The use or provision of media in parenting activities in kindergarten is adjusted to the material to be delivered. The use of the method in parenting activities in parenting management meetings uses the lecture, discussion and question and answer method because it is considered very good and effective, especially the target of this parenting activity is parents or adults because the implementation of the parenting program is carried out in the form of counseling, so the counseling material must be related to focus on child education.

This program of providing material for parents is often called a parenting program. The program is given to parents in providing knowledge about the growth and development of children so that parents can take care of their children according to their growth and development period and can provide good and correct parenting. So with this parenting program, not only educators participate in optimizing children's growth and development, but also parents participate in optimizing children's growth and development, so that later they can be useful for society, nation, state and religion. Even the role of parents is more important because it is parents who take care of their children.

3. Evaluation of Parenting Program Management

The evaluation process is a measuring tool to determine the extent to which the objectives of a program can be achieved. The evaluation process in the parenting program can be said as a form of assessment of an activity that has been carried out. This is considering the notion of evaluation according to Martha (2009) evaluation of activities is an attempt to measure and provide value objectively on the achievement of the results of the implementation of activities that have been previously planned. Evaluation always seeks to question the effectiveness and efficiency of implementing a plan. In addition, evaluation also measures the results of the implementation objectively with a size that can be accepted by all parties concerned.

Evaluation of parenting programs in Kindergarten is carried out in the following ways:

- a. assess changes in attitudes and unpretentious communication between parents and their children,
- b. the activeness of parents in parenting activities
- c. weekly developmental assessment of the child
- d. The use of funds is known directly by each student's guardian.

Daeng Arifin (2014:40) has carried out periodic evaluations over time. After a certain period of time has passed but the performance indicators are still below the target, it is necessary to analyze and take corrective action. In this case, it is better to carry out the Plan-Do-Check-Action planning cycle which is now widely adopted by various organizations in carrying out their organizational programs and activities, this discussion about PDCA can be given in a separate session

Instilling an understanding of parenting material is not an easy job, when a school determines parenting material, it is hoped that in particular it can be conveyed well to parents and carry out and apply it to their children with pleasure, it is not uncommon for parents to choose not to heed the parenting materials that have been held at school.

Evaluation of the parenting program is carried out to find out the advantages and disadvantages of the parenting program that has been implemented, so that the implementation of the next parenting program will be even better, and learn from mistakes made during the previous parenting program. So planning before implementing a parenting program is really needed, so that a program can run well. The implementation of a good parenting program must be in accordance with what has been planned. Evaluation of parenting programs is carried out to find out the advantages and disadvantages of the programs that have been implemented so that future programs can learn from experience.

The results of the study based on observations and interviews showed that the evaluation of the parenting program was carried out first by the head of the institution together with the teacher in semester and annual meetings. Evaluation is carried out periodically by the head of the kindergarten by requesting a report either directly or in writing to the homeroom teacher. The head of the kindergarten in addition to requesting a report to the class teacher and the parenting service section. This evaluation is carried out by the head of the kindergarten as a measure of the extent to which the parenting program is implemented. Researchers also conducted interviews with parents of students who have outstanding children who previously had problems with their children, so that researchers know that parenting programs can increase parental participation in learning activities in kindergarten.

In the evaluation aspect, all components have been carried out by the head of the kindergarten as the holder and policy maker, the head of the institution provides periodic evaluations to classroom teachers because they play an active role in providing parenting program services. Daily feedback by classroom teachers can provide early detection of kindergarten principals if there are problems experienced by students, so that institutions can immediately handle and find solutions.

D. CONCLUSION

Muhaimah Kindergarten in West Bandung Regency has implemented a parenting program including lesson planning compiled by the teacher, parenting organization, parenting program implementation involving parents and the environment, and evaluation, as well as various solutions to overcome these obstacles. What the teachers have done refers to the management of the parenting program which causes the role of parents in the implementation of the parenting program to increase even though it is not significant.

In planning the parenting program in kindergarten, it is arranged based on parenting problems and motivates parents to always play an active role in every activity program organized by the school, although not comprehensively. And the organization that has been carried out so far has not involved all staff in kindergarten, so that the delivery of parenting programs if not the

principal or presenters from outside the classroom teacher has not played an active role in delivering parenting programs to parents so that parenting programs have not been effective and efficient.

The implementation of the parenting program from initial activities, core activities, and final activities has been carried out, but there are still some parents who do not follow and obey the rules, this is due to the busyness of their respective parents, then there are those who arrive late or do not follow parenting until finished so that it does not follow parenting from the beginning or until it is done. Lack of parents in understanding the material presented between the presenters and parents in providing an overview regarding the collection of various evidences about child development in the parenting material being discussed.

Teachers are less creative in the use of parenting methods, parenting media, limited facilities and infrastructure are also obstacles in implementing parenting programs. The solutions to overcome various obstacles faced during parenting program activities include involving teachers in training or workshops, then the principal provides directions on how to use, maintain, take responsibility for damage, and maintain the safety of parenting media.

Efforts to overcome school facilities and infrastructure by collaborating with related parties both to foundations, school committees, local stakeholders and the education office, although the results are not optimal. The recommendations of this research are information material for the development of further research, and research implementation with the aim of implementing parenting programs in Kindergartens in West Bandung Regency and providing an overview or reference on how the parenting program in kindergartens is, and it is hoped that there will be a continuation of the research. This is more about knowing the parenting program.

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